

THE PLACE OF INTUITIVE KNOWLEDGE AMONG THE TYPES OF PHILOSOPHICAL KNOWLEDGE

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Abstract In the article, about the content of the Russian scientist V.F. Asmus's book on the history of the development of the problem of intuition in philosophy and mathematics, intuition is considered as a fact of knowledge, that is, among the types of knowledge in philosophy, it is determined by intuitive knowledge or intuition. His views on the existence of direct knowledge, under this direct knowledge, intuition determines the direct choice of reality, the objective connection of things.

Key words: intuition, intuition, truth, knowledge, intuition, discretion.

According to V.F.Asmus, among the types of knowledge in philosophy there is direct knowledge, which is considered separately, which is determined by intuitive knowledge or intuition. Under direct knowledge, he defines the direct will of truth, the will that is not based on proving the objective connection of things. The first form of such knowledge, as they say, is the direct perception of reality by means of external senses. Such knowledge, first of all, differs in direct character, it does not need to be proved¹. For example, to be sure that I see a white object, there is no need to prove the truth of this volition. The truth will be revealed directly. Secondly, in all such cases, the direct access to reality is achieved with the help of senses: sight, hearing, smell, touch, etc. In relation to direct evidence, this knowledge is knowledge sensitive to the source of knowledge².

¹ Salimov Baxriddin Lutfullaevich. The philosophical role of dialectical categories in human life. Oriental Renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences. Volume: 1, Issue 6, 2021. - P.406-410.

² Эрнийёзов Ў.К. ЯНГИ ДАВР ҒАРБ МУТАФАККИРЛАРИНИНГ ИНТЕЛЛЕКТУАЛ ИНТУИЦИЯ – ҲАҚИДАГИ ҚАРАШЛАРИ // Oriental Renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences. 2022. - № 2. – Б. 5. (№ 5; SJIF : 5.947).

V.F.Asmus singles out vision, which is the most important of all emotions, and explains it directly. And in this context, he explains the definition of the concept of intuition from the Latin word *intuitus* as thinking, volition, seeing, that is, volition by seeing. V.F.Asmus stated that "the terms intellectual intuition, emotional intuition mean only a certain reality or a type of knowledge, and there is no need to connect them with a certain philosophical theory that explains the fact of intuitive manifestation. V.F.Asmus understands that intellectual intuition cannot directly perceive the truth, prove it, or obtain it only through external feelings, and emphasizes that there are no principled objections to the use of such a term³.

Intuition as a fact of knowledge is an indisputable fact that exists in the field of knowledge for all knowers as a type of knowledge⁴. But as a theory of the facts of knowledge, each theory of intuition is divided from philosophical theories into the following: idealistic or materialistic, metaphysical or dialectical. Intuition is one of the philosophical theories that have epistemological doctrines that explain the facts of knowledge, either directly or intuitively. V.F.Asmus, in his work, many scientists and whole schools of mathematics (for example, the school of intuitionism represented by Weyl, Brauer, Gatening, etc.) with the term intuition, apart from its non-philosophical meaning, have a purely idealistic philosophical significance states that⁵.

In general, V.F.Asmus's book devoted to the development of the problem of intuitive knowledge in philosophy and mathematics in the XVII-early XX centuries has set and solved three main tasks. "His task is, first of all, to make a clear distinction between intuition as a fact of knowledge and as philosophical

³ Эрнийёзов Ў.К. ЯНГИ ДАВР ҒАРБ МУТАФАККИРЛАРИНИНГ ИНТЕЛЛЕКТУАЛ ИНТУИЦИЯ – ҲАҚИДАГИ ҚАРАШЛАРИ // Oriental Renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences. 2022. - № 2. – Б. 5. (№ 5; SJIF : 5.947).

⁴ Салимов Бахриддин Лутфуллаевич (2020). ФИЛОСОФСКОЕ РОЛЬ ДИАЛЕКТИЧЕСКИХ КАТЕГОРИЙ В ЖИЗНИ ЧЕЛОВЕКА. Историческая психология и социология истории, 13 (1), 111-119.

⁵ Салимов Бахриддин Лутфуллаевич (2020). Жизненный путь природы и общества состоит из цепи случайностей и необходимостей. Colloquium-journal, (24 (76)), 55-57. doi: 10.24411/2520-6990-2020-12159.

theories of intuition⁶. If a philosopher recognizes the existence of intuitive knowledge among other types of knowledge, then this recognition itself does not say anything about whether the philosopher's theory of intuition is materialistic or idealistic. To judge this solely on the basis of the philosopher's recognition of the existence of intuition is as wrong as judging the philosopher's character on the basis of the philosopher's claim that all knowledge ultimately comes back to feeling⁷.

The second task is to establish specific features among the philosophical theories of sequential intuition in the history of the philosophy of the new era. First of all, it is necessary to distinguish rationalist theories of intuition, as well as theories of intuition developed by German idealists and romantics in the late 18th and early 19th centuries, from theories called intuitionism, which appeared in philosophical idealism. Theories of intuition, that is, philosophical theories about intuition doctrines developed by Plato, Neoplatonists, Descartes, Leibniz, Kant and Fichte and their contemporaries Hamann and Jacobi, Schelling and Friedrich Schlegel, Goethe and Schopenhauer, and in the 20th century - Bergson and Lossky, Husserl and Benedetto Croce, etc. But their it would be a clear mistake to think of everything as 'intuitive' - for example Bergson. Not every theory of intuition is a theory of intuitionism. "Intuitionism is a very specific historical form of the philosophical doctrine of intuition⁸.

According to V.F.Asmus, the teachings of philosophers of the 20th century appeared on the basis of knowledge about intuition, rationalist understanding of knowledge. "They do not have the opposition of intuitive and logical thinking, but they consider intuition as the highest intellectual type of knowledge. V.F.Asmus,

⁶ Салимов Бахриддин Лутфуллаевич (2020). ФИЛОСОФСКОЕ РОЛЬ ДИАЛЕКТИЧЕСКИХ КАТЕГОРИЙ В ЖИЗНИ ЧЕЛОВЕКА. Историческая психология и социология истории, 13 (1), 111-119.

⁷ Эрнестов Ў.К. ЯНГИ ДАВР ҒАРБ МУТАҒАККИРЛАРИНИНГ ИНТЕЛЛЕКТУАЛ ИНТУИЦИЯ – ҲАҚИДАГИ ҚАРАШЛАРИ // Oriental Renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences. 2022. - № 2. – Б. 5. (№ 5; SJIF : 5.947).

⁸ Салимов Бахриддин Лутфуллаевич (2020). Жизненный путь природы и общества состоит из цепи случайностей и необходимостей. Colloquium-journal, (24 (76)), 55-57. doi: 10.24411/2520-6990-2020-12159.

on the other hand, sees reason as a form of criticism, a direction that is skeptical of science and its logical apparatus. This trend includes a rejection of intellectual methods of knowing and a lack of confidence in the ability of science to adequately know the truth⁹. In this regard, the third task of Asmus's book is to prove the failure of intuitionism. Since the doctrine of intuition has been revived on a rational basis in modern mathematics¹⁰, where he relies on the very valuable achievements of intuitionistic (constructivist) mathematics, the fourth task was to oppose the book to decadent, "illogical" intuitionism (eg, Bergson). An example of this is not only the doctrines of intuition developed by mathematicians and rationalists of the 17th century, but also the doctrines of intuition that appeared in mathematics in the first quarter of the 20th century.

The concept of intuition and philosophical teachings about intuition originated in ancient Indian and ancient Greek philosophies. The theories of intuition created by Renaissance philosophers, especially Nicholas of Cusa and Giordano Bruno, are also very interesting. However, the ancient theories of intuition that appeared during the Renaissance are not the subject of this work. In Asmus's book, the problem of intuition in philosophy and mathematics. Considers theories of intuition only from the rationalism of the 20th century¹¹. The development of mathematics and natural science, closely related to the epistemological problems facing philosophy, determined the specific features of the ideas, concepts, and teachings about intuition developed in the 20th century. The theories of intuition put forward in the 19th and 20th centuries cannot be

⁹ Эрнийёзов Ў.К. ЯНГИ ДАВР ҒАРБ МУТАҒАККИРЛАРИНИНГ ИНТЕЛЛЕКТУАЛ ИНТУИЦИЯ – ҲАҚИДАГИ ҚАРАШЛАРИ // Oriental Renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences. 2022. - № 2. – Б. 5. (№ 5; SJIF : 5.947).

¹⁰ Salimov Baxriddin Lutfullaevich. The philosophical role of dialectical categories in human life. Oriental Renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences. Volume: 1, Issue 6, 2021. - P.406-410.

¹¹ Салимов Бахриддин Лутфуллаевич (2020). Жизненный путь природы и общества состоит из цепи случайностей и необходимостей. Colloquium-journal, (24 (76)), 55-57. doi: 10.24411/2520-6990-2020-12159. Salimov Baxriddin Lutfullaevich. The philosophical role of dialectical categories in human life. Oriental Renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences. Volume: 1, Issue 6, 2021. -P.406-410.

considered only as philosophical theories, without taking into account their conditioning by the logical nature of modern mathematical, natural and social sciences. The history of the development of these teachings is of great interest due to the connection between the philosophical doctrines of intuition and the natural and mathematical sciences¹².

V. F. Asmus emphasizes that the content of the theories of intuition discussed in his book responded to class interests and was caused by socio-historical reasons¹³. According to him, studying the history of the development of philosophical ideas, concepts, theories of intuition, we are sure that the theoretical root of the philosophical misconceptions contained in them is not only idealism. A metaphysical way of thinking that separates the will of the mind from living, emotional thinking, but also makes the distinction between direct and mediate knowledge absolute and fails to identify the true path to knowledge development¹⁴, - he understands.

Historians of philosophy have neglected the problem of intuition, underestimating the importance of the differences between the doctrines that have replaced each other and theories of intuition. They did not determine the importance of the problem of intuition in the theory of scientific knowledge, although the problem of science and scientific knowledge was raised in the history of philosophy, it should be noted that for more than two thousand years of history, the problem of intuition in the philosophical theory of knowledge had very different and at the same time certain solutions. took¹⁵.

¹² Салимов Бахриддин Лутфуллаевич (2020). Жизненный путь природы и общества состоит из цепи случайностей и необходимостей. *Colloquium-journal*, (24 (76)), 55-57. doi: 10.24411/2520-6990-2020-12159.

¹³ Салимов Бахриддин Лутфуллаевич (2020). Жизненный путь природы и общества состоит из цепи случайностей и необходимостей. *Colloquium-journal*, (24 (76)), 55-57. doi: 10.24411/2520-6990-2020-12159.

¹⁴ Салимов Бахриддин Лутфуллаевич (2020). ФИЛОСОФСКАЯ РОЛЬ ДИАЛЕКТИЧЕСКИХ КАТЕГОРИЙ В ЖИЗНИ ЧЕЛОВЕКА. *Историческая психология и социология истории*, 13 (1), 111-119.

¹⁵ Салимов Бахриддин Лутфуллаевич (2020). ФИЛОСОФСКАЯ РОЛЬ ДИАЛЕКТИЧЕСКИХ КАТЕГОРИЙ В ЖИЗНИ ЧЕЛОВЕКА. *Историческая психология и социология истории*, 13 (1), 111-119.

ADABIYOTLAR

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